

Comparative Efficiency of Some Indian Gums as Emulsion Stabilisers

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A detailed study of emulsions stabilised by some gums was done by the method of King and Mukerjee on the ageing emulsions. Gum Khair was found to be the best stabiliser for kerosene oil followed closely by sahjan > karaya > ghatty > neem > katira > modal gum > gonj gum (using 1% emulsifier). The nature of oil played an important role so far as the type of emulsion produced was concerned. The order of the stability coefficients in case of olive oil emulsions was changed as follows : ghatty > sahjan > karaya > khair > neem gum.

In continuation with the previous work² on the stability coefficients of some Indian gums, it was considered desirable and useful to extend the study to the previous reported gums along with some other gums. A survey of the literature reveals that almost no work has been done on the comparative efficiency of the following gums reported in this communication. This situation has prompted the present investigation.

- (1) *Sterulia urens* (Gum karaya)
- (2) *Moringa petrygosperma* (Sahjan gum)
- (3) *Acacia catechu* (Khair gum)
- (4) *Cochlospermum religiosum* (Katira gum)
- (5) *Anogeissus latifolia* (Ghatty gum)
- (6) *Lannea grandis* gum (Modal gum)
- (7) *Melica indica* (Syn : *Azodirachta indica*)
- (8) *Derriis scandens* (Leguminosae) (Gonj gum).

EXPERIMENTAL

Purification of gums : The crude gums were dried in vacuo at about 100° and then powdered in a pestle and mortar. The powdered gums were then purified by methods of Ingle and Bhide⁴ and V. M. Patrikh, Ingle and Bhide⁵. One p.c. suspension of each gum was made by heating the gum with distilled water on a water bath.

1. A. King and L. N. Mukerjee, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1939, **58**, 243.
2. L. N. Mukerjee and S. D. Shukla, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 805.
3. L. N. Mukerjee and S. D. Shukla, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1965, **28**, 177; 1967, **30**, 187.
4. T. R. Ingle and B. V. Bhide, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **31**, 939.
5. V. M. Parikh, T. R. Ingle and B. V. Bhide, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **33**, 120.

Preparation of emulsions and size frequency analysis : Emulsions in case of each gum were prepared at 30° by King and Mukerjee's¹ method using the above prepared suspensions and keeping the ratio of suspension to oil (kerosene and olive) as 60 : 40. Size frequency analysis of these emulsions was done immediately and on regular intervals as indicated on the ageing emulsions. The stability coefficients were computed from the data on specific surfaces of these emulsions applying the theory of least squares as described in earlier work^{2,3}.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A large number of emulsions of kerosene oil and olive oil stabilised by different agents were prepared and size frequency analysis was done immediately and after different intervals thereafter. The results are too numerous to quote in full but a representative selection is given in Table 1. The number of emulsions refer to the summarised results of Table 3, the suffix to the length of time in weeks, which elapsed between emulsification and analysis. In all these cases the emulsion had been homogenised.

TABLE 1

Percentage distribution of oil droplets of different sizes in homogenised emulsions. (Indices over the emulsion no. denote the number of weeks that have elapsed).

Mean diameter (μ)	1 ⁰	1 ¹	1 ²	1 ³	1 ⁴	1 ⁵	13 ⁰	13 ¹	13 ²	13 ³	13 ⁴	13 ⁵
5	92.25	88.85	86.90	85.38	83.02	81.70	93.55	82.10	—	77.11	74.91	69.92
10	7.75	9.91	11.01	11.65	12.84	13.68	6.45	14.07	—	14.45	16.42	15.83
15	—	1.24	2.09	2.97	4.14	4.62	—	3.83	—	6.01	5.28	7.65
20	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	2.43	2.45	3.43
25	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.94	2.11
30	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1.06
Free oil separation (p.c.)							nil					
Agent	1.0% Gum Karaya						1.0% Gum Neem					

The results of these tables are all concerned with kerosene oil emulsions; olive oil emulsions are very similar except in a few marked cases. It is interesting that in all cases the degree of dispersion of the freshly prepared emulsion is great.

In the case of khair stabilised emulsion the initial dispersion varied between 5 μ (97.75%) to 10 μ (2.25%). There was no gradual increase in the size of the particle globules in the course of 2 months, only the percentage of globules of the two sizes showed variations. Even after two months the smallest globules had a percentage as high as 92.84 and there was no oil separation. The emulsions were initially fine and continued to be so even after 2 months.

Sahjan gum represented a similar behaviour so far as a dispersion of particles is concerned with a slight change in the percentage of particle sizes i.e., from 92.72% to 84.35 in case of 5 μ particles.

Neem gum and *Derris scandens* gum stabilised emulsions were very unsuitable, although initially very fine. The emulsions of latter broke after one month and there was plenty of oil separation. In both these cases the emulsions were fine in the beginning but rapid coarsening took place from the first week and particles upto 30μ size were visible after one month's storage but the coarsening was greater in case of latter. There was no oil separation in the case of neem gum even after 2 months.

Lannea grandis and katira gums had almost similar dispersion of particles after 1 week's storage, coarsening took place in a similar manner from first week (particles upto 20μ were visible in both the cases), although in case of fresh emulsions of *Lannea grandis* particles of only 5μ to 10μ were visible while in case of latter particles of 15μ (8.39%) were also visible. After one month's storage time *Lannea grandis* represented the maximum coarsening as particles of size upto 30μ were seen.

Katira gum represented the coarsest emulsion from the beginning. Particles upto 15μ were visible, the percentage being 8.39. After 2 months' storage a fair percentage of globules of sizes 15μ , 20μ and 25μ were present. In case of *Lannea grandis* gum there was no oil separation but this was observed in the case of katira gum.

TABLE 2

Specific area and separation of oil from emulsions on various intervals of time

Emulsion no.	Agents	Specific area in sq. cm/gm. oil (all values $\times 10^3$)					Oil used	
		Immediately	After 1 week	After 2 weeks	After 3 weeks	After 4 weeks		After 8 weeks
1	1.0% Gum Karaya	11.62	10.07	9.41	8.92	8.39	8.19	K. Oil
2	1.0% Gum Karaya	9.82	9.60	9.49	8.22	6.99	5.14	Olive oil
3	1.0% Sahjan Gum	11.74	11.03	10.99	10.95	10.52	10.20	K. Oil
4	1.0% Sahjan Gum	7.66	7.15	5.91	5.55	5.13	4.81	Olive oil
5	1.0% Gum Khair	13.41	13.01	12.90	12.66	12.43	11.77	K. Oil
6	1.0% Gum Khair	11.24	11.22	11.15	10.44	9.91	8.66	Olive Oil
7	1.0% Katira Gum	7.05	6.38	5.33 (0.5)	4.75 (1.0)	4.23 (1.5)	3.99 (3.0)	K. Oil
8	1.0% Katira Gum	—	—	—	—	—	—	Olive Oil
9	1.0% Gum Ghatty	12.96	12.68	12.18	11.76	11.16	7.66	K. Oil
10	1.0% Gum Ghatty	11.48	11.45	11.30	10.92	9.45	8.79	Olive Oil
11	1.0% Modal Gum	10.26	5.79	5.63	4.12	3.59	3.52	K. Oil
12	1.0% Modal Gum	—	—	—	—	—	—	Olive Oil
13	1.0% Neem Gum	11.96	8.44	—	6.49	5.85	4.54	K. Oil
14	1.0% Neem Gum	11.37	—	—	4.34 (17.2)	3.47 (18.4)	2.31 (20.0)	Olive Oil
15	1.0% Gonj Gum	7.88	5.94 (0.5)	4.48 (1.0)	4.46 (1.5)	3.39 (2.5)	Broken	K. Oil
16	1.0% Gonj Gum	—	—	—	—	—	—	Olive Oil

(Quantities in parenthesis being the percentage oil separation on a particular day).

Stability of emulsions : The need for quantitative method of evaluating emulsions has long been felt. A few workers have attempted the classification of emulsifying agents according to their efficiency in stabilising emulsions. These limited comparisons are all of qualitative nature. This problem of an emulsifying agent is essentially the same as that of qualitative measurement on emulsion stability and can only be solved satisfactorily by the study of change of interfacial area with time and change of various environmental factors.

From the point of view of emulsion stability, the distribution of the various droplet sizes discussed above is less important than the variation of the total interface with time. We have therefore collected in Table 2 the values of the total area of interface per gm of oil as calculated from the size frequency analysis of emulsion of different ages. The change of specific area values may be plotted against time as abscissa for different emulsions to illustrate the agreement between the data on the change of specific surface with time and the exponential hypothesis and the lines determined by fitting the data to the equation.

$$-\frac{d\sigma}{dt} = K'\sigma = \frac{\sigma}{K}$$

(where σ = specific surface, K' = instability coefficient, and K = stability coefficient) by the method of least squares. The linear curves in all cases represent the degradation of emulsions, hence a measurement of slopes provides a qualitative comparison of stability. Accordingly the slope of each curve is measured and divided by the graphically determined

TABLE 3

Data for 40% kerosene oil and olive oil emulsions

Emul- sion no.	Emulsifier	Oil	Type of emulsion produced	Stability coefficient $K \times 10^3$
1	1.0% Gum Karaya	K	(O/W)	52.22
2	1.0% Gum Karaya	O	(O/W)	17.82
3	1.0% Sahjan Gum	K	(O/W)	107.99
4	1.0% Sahjan Gum	O	(O/W)	19.40
5	1.0% Gum Khair	K	(O/W)	120.36
6	1.0% Gum Khair	O	(O/W)	15.00
7	1.0% Katira Gum	K	(O/W)	14.50
8	1.0% Katira Gum	O	(W/O)	—
9	1.0% Gum Ghatty	K	(O/W)	24.12
10	1.0% Gum Ghatty	O	(O/W)	54.14
11	1.0% Modal Gum	K	(O/W)	9.89
12	1.0% Modal Gum	O	(W/O)	—
13	1.0% Neem Gum	K	(O/W)	19.73
14	1.0% Neem Gum	O	(O/W)	8.52
15	1.0% Gonj Gum	K	(O/W)	5.82
16	1.0% Gonj Gum	O	(W/O)	—

initial interface (σ_0) to furnish the rate of decrease per unit area of interface. This is termed the instability factor and might be defined as the decrease of each cm^2 of fresh emulsion per day. The reciprocal of this would be a direct measure of emulsion stability (K). The stability coefficient values are collected in Table 3.

With all these gums, there is a decrease of specific interfacial area with time. The variations are comparatively slower. One is tempted to compare the stabilities of these emulsions by means of the time of half break which can be obtained by plotting the specific area of interface against time and reading off the time taken for the specific area of the given specimen to diminish to half its initial value. If we compare the specific area values of kerosene emulsions all containing 1% of the agent we find that with gum karaya the initial sp. area of 11.62 is reduced to 8.19 i.e., roughly $3/4$ of its initial value in 8 weeks. This clearly shows that gum karaya stabilised emulsion is very stable. With khair the initial area of 13.41 is reduced to 11.77 in the same time. This should be equally stable. With gum ghatty the initial value of 12.96 becomes 7.66 i.e., nearly half in 2 months. Naturally it is much inferior to the first two. With neem gum and modal gum the initial interface areas of 11.96 and 10.26 are reduced to 6.49 and 4.12 respectively. But the stability factors of these contradict the conclusion derived above. The time of half break may thus give misleading values.

From the data of Table 3 it is obvious that the stability of these emulsions and their general behaviour cannot be obtained by mere knowledge of the initial size frequency analysis nor by their half period break. The emulsions most finely dispersed are in no way more stable than the coarser samples.

Influence of oil : On trying the same gums with olive oil interesting results were obtained. Except khair, karaya and sahjan, ghatty and neem gums all the other three gums (namely *Lannea grandis*, *Derris scandens* and katira) gave W/O emulsions while the former gums gave O/W type of emulsions like kerosene oil emulsions of these gums.

With these agents, the globule size distribution and stability seem to vary considerably with the nature of oil. This variation is rather specific with different agents but some sort of general tendency can be deduced.

Olive oil emulsions are generally coarser from the very beginning and become much coarser on standing in comparison to kerosene emulsions i.e., particles of $5-15\mu$ were visible in the beginning, particles of 20μ (3.94%) were also visible after 2 weeks and after 8 weeks particles of 5μ were decreased (from 75.27% to 58.47%) and particles as big as 25μ (2.59%) were also visible. There was no separation of oil in any one of the O/W emulsions of olive oil except in case of neem gum.

Ghatty and neem gum stabilised olive oil emulsions were finer as compared to kerosene oil emulsions. But deterioration of neem stabilised emulsion took place rapidly. 20% oil was separated in this case after 2 months standing.

Khair gum and sahjan gum stabilised emulsions are most stable in case of kerosene oil emulsions, the stabilities being 120.36 and 107.99 respectively. Karaya stabilised emulsions have got stability coefficient 52.22 which is nearly half of that of sahjan gum stabilised

emulsion. Ghatty, neem and katira gums have got nearly same values of stability coefficients with slight decrease from ghatty to katira. Modal gum and gonj gum are the poor stabilisers of kerosene oil emulsions as is evident from the stability coefficient values as given in table no. 3.

The marked influence of oil on the values of stability coefficients can also be seen from the table 3. Katira, modal and gonj gums gave W/O types of emulsions which broke in a very short time of storage and the stability coefficient values could not be found in these cases by the present method. Except in case of ghatty gum the stability coefficients in all cases were diminished from the corresponding values in case of kerosene oil stabilised emulsions. In case of ghatty gum there was a definite increase from 24.12 (kerosene oil) to 54.14 in case of olive oil.

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